

1 **Tacstd2 and surface antigen expression in embryonic development.**

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7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
8 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here Tacstd2 and
9 surface antigen expression in embryonic development.
10 Among markers of pluripotency and embryonic state we discovered included Plac5, Ca5b and other
11 carbonic anhydrases, as well as other placental and pluripotency associated transcripts.

12 Citations

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